

Third Dissociation Constant of Phosphoric Acid from 283.15 K to 323.15 K

A. K. GHOSH, J. C. GHOSH and B. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-5

Manuscript received 6 August 1980, accepted 9 September 1980

Third dissociation constant of phosphoric acid has been determined from 283.15K to 323.15K in steps of 5K by finding the hydrolysis constant K_h of HPO_4^{2-} . pK_h has been determined from e.m.f. measurement of cell (C-1) utilising modified Davies equation.

Between 283.15K and 323.15K, pK_s fits in the equation, $pK_s = \frac{2397.4}{T} + 4.2364 -$

$2.6061 \times 10^{-3}T + 8.3834 \times 10^{-5}T^2$. The thermodynamic quantities ΔH_s° , ΔG_s° , ΔS_s° and ΔCp_s° have also been determined at these temperatures. At 298.15K these values are 5175J mol⁻¹, 68264J mol⁻¹, -212J mol⁻¹K⁻¹ and -559J mol⁻¹K⁻¹ respectively.

ACCURATE values of the third dissociation constant of phosphoric acid over a number of temperatures are not known. A number of workers have determined pK_s either at one (mostly 298.15K) or two temperatures or rather at high ionic strength. Chief among these determinations are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1— pK_s OF PHOSPHORIC ACID

Method	pK_s	Temp/K	Reference
Conductivity and distribution ratio of ammonium phosphate	11.89	298.15	1
Potentiometric titration	12.30	291.15	2
pH of a mixture of sec. and tert. phosphates	12.66	311.15	3
e.m.f. of quinhydrone-calomel cell	12.10	298.15	4
Hydrolysis of tert. phosphate	11.99	293.15	5
	11.83	311.15	
e.m.f. of cells with liquid junction potential	12.325	298.15	6
pH	11.83	311.15	7
Colorimetry	11.70 to 11.95	298.15	8
Spectrophotometric study of mixtures of $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 - \text{NaHCO}_3$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 - \text{NaOH}$	12.375	298.15	9
Laser study of solution of orthophosphates of Na and K	11.921	298.15	10

Many of these pK_s values do not correspond to thermodynamic dissociation constant. Neither the pK_s values nor the thermodynamic quantities corresponding to the third stage of dissociation of phosphoric acid are known at a number of temperatures.

This led us to study cell (C-1).

It was observed that when $m_1 : m_3 = 1 : 1$, the Ag/AgCl, Cl⁻ electrode was sluggish and the bias potential went on increasing with time. The bias potential decreased when $m_1 : m_3 = 1 : 2$ and disappeared altogether when $m_1 : m_3 = 1 : 3$. It seemed that the bias potential was due to slow adsorption of phosphate on Ag/AgCl electrodes which was prevented when Cl⁻ concentration increased. So $m_1 : m_3$ was kept equal to 1 : 3 while $m_1 : m_2$ had to be kept between 1 : 6 to 1 : 8 to have an adequate concentration of PO_4^{3-} . The stoichiometric concentrations were correct to a micromol kg⁻¹.

Experimental

$\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaOH and NaCl used for the preparation of solutions were each G.R. samples of E. Merck. Their purities were checked by standard methods¹¹. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water of conductivity $< 0.5 \times 10^{-6}$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Carbonate-free NaOH solution was kept in polythene bottles in an atmosphere of N_2 until use. NaCl was found free from bromide and iodide¹². Two stock solutions were prepared—solution 'A' containing Na_2HPO_4 and NaCl in mole ratio of 1 : 3 and solution 'B' was a standard solution of carbonate-free NaOH kept in an atmosphere of N_2 . Experimental solutions were prepared by taking weighed amounts of 'A' and 'B' and diluting the mixture appropriately in a weighed measuring flask. All weighings were corrected for buoyancy.

The experimental solutions were deoxygenated by passing pure presaturated N_2 for 12 to 14 hours and were then introduced under pressure of N_2 into

the conventional 'H'-shaped electrode vessel. One limb of the electrode vessel was fitted up with Ag/AgCl electrode. The other limb also contained the experimental solution but no electrode to begin with. Previous to filling up the electrode vessel with experimental solution, it was completely flushed out with pure presaturated N_2 . Ag/AgCl electrodes were prepared by thermal electrolytic^{1,3} method and hydrogen electrodes were prepared according to standard methods^{1,4}. A cushion of N_2 gas was allowed to remain between the stopper of the limbs containing Ag/AgCl, Cl^- electrodes and the solution. The stopper of the interconnecting tube was then closed and the electrode vessel together with the presaturators were thermostated at $\pm 0.05K$. Electrolytic H_2 gas supplied by Indian Oxygen Ltd. was passed successively through a column filled with KOH pellets, a 30 cm $\times$ 2 cm column of reduced copper heated to ca 780 K, another column of KOH pellets, a sintered glass plate of pore size G 0 and then through two presaturators. Pure and presaturated H_2 gas thus obtained was bubbled through the other limb at the rate of 3 or 4 bubbles per sec. A slower rate of bubbling took a long time to produce equilibrium. After two hours hydrogen electrodes rinsed with the experimental solution were introduced in the other limb. Thereafter e.m.f. reading was taken every half an hour after opening the interconnecting stop cock. A Tinsley Vernier potentiometer (type 4363) coupled with a Bajaj galvanometer of sensitivity 3.92×10^{-10} amp mm⁻¹ was used for the purpose. E.M.F.'s were compared against a certified Weston cadmium cell of Cambridge Instrument Co. Constant e.m.f. values were obtained after 5 to 6 hours of the introduction of hydrogen electrode Duplicate cells were set up. The e.m.f. values recorded in Tables 2 to 10 are the mean of the duplicate readings after applying correction for barometric pressure, vapour pressure and bubbler depth^{1,5}. The e.m.f. of the duplicate cells agreed within 0.05 mV. The molalities of the various ionic species were found as discussed below.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) is given by $E = E^\circ - k \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl}$, where $k = \frac{2.3026RT}{F}$. This equation may be written as $E = E^\circ - k \log \frac{K_w}{a_{OH}} \cdot a_{Cl}$, since $K_w = a_H \cdot a_{OH}$ as a_{H_2O} is taken to be unity for dilute solutions. Or,

$$E = E^\circ - k \log K_w - k \log \frac{m_{Cl}}{m_{OH}} - k \log \frac{\gamma_{Cl}}{\gamma_{OH}} \dots (1)$$

In a previous communication^{1,6} we found that modified Davies equation may be taken to be valid in alkaline solution. So, applying modified Davies equation to (1) we get,

$$\log m_{OH} = \frac{(E - E^\circ)}{k} + \log K_w + \log m_{Cl} + (\beta_{Cl} - \beta_{OH})\mu \dots (2)$$

In cell solution of cell (C-1) when the m_{OH} is much greater than $m_{HPO_4^{2-}}$ it is presumed that the reaction (3) takes place,

The ionic strength μ is given by equation (4).

$$\mu = 3m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + 2x \dots (4)$$

where $x = m_{PO_4} = m_2 - m_{OH}$

The hydrolysis of PO_4^{3-} is represented in equation (3). Assuming a_{H_2O} to be unity,

$$K_h = \frac{m_{HPO_4} \cdot m_{OH}}{m_{PO_4}} \times \frac{\gamma_{HPO_4} \cdot \gamma_{OH}}{\gamma_{PO_4}} \dots (5)$$

Henceforth charges are left out for neatness. Putting

$$K_H = \frac{m_{HPO_4} \cdot m_{OH}}{m_{PO_4}} \text{ and applying modified Davies}$$

equation to (5) we get,

$$\log K_h = \log K_H + \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \beta'_3 \mu$$

which on transformation is reduced to (6).

$$\log K_H + \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_h + \beta'_3 \mu \dots (6)$$

where $\beta'_3 = (\beta_{PO_4} - \beta_{HPO_4} - \beta_{OH})$.

Now taking $\mu = 3m_1 + m_2 + m_3$ and utilising the values of $(\beta_{Cl} - \beta_{OH})$ and K_w reported elsewhere^{1,6} we get a value of m_{OH} from equation (2). The values of k , E° and A required for this purpose is obtainable from literature^{1,7-1,9}. This value of m_{OH} is now substituted in equation (4) to get a value of 'x' and hence a new value of μ . The process of iteration is repeated till we get constant and consistent values of m_{OH} , m_{HPO_4} , m_{PO_4} and μ correct to a micromol kg⁻¹. The values of K_H are then calculated. These values have been recorded in Tables 2 to 10.

Plots of L.H.S. of equation(6) against μ (some of which are shown in Fig. 1) at all the temperatures studied were straight lines—the maximum deviation of the points being less than 0.03 mV. The intercept of the lines on extrapolation to $\mu = 0$ give values of $\log K_h$ and the slopes give β'_3 . These values were also obtained statistically from least square analysis and are tabulated in Table 11. Both the values agreed closely with one another. pK_s was now obtained from equation (7).

$$pK_s = pK_w - pK_h \dots (7)$$

TABLE 2

Temp. 283.15K

Stoichiometric Molalities and Ionic Strengths in Cell (C-1)

$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002398	0.015863	0.007196	1.06396	0.0003188	0.013784	0.002079	0.034433	3.635
0.003195	0.023513	0.009587	1.06672	0.0002760	0.020594	0.002919	0.048523	3.648
0.003981	0.027552	0.011944	1.06495	0.0003175	0.023889	0.003663	0.059764	3.703
0.004782	0.033366	0.014349	1.06510	0.0003289	0.028913	0.004453	0.070967	3.747
0.005571	0.039725	0.016717	1.06569	0.0003215	0.034476	0.005249	0.083779	3.770
0.007220	0.047294	0.021666	1.06317	0.0004028	0.040476	0.006818	0.104302	3.863

TABLE 3

Temp. 288.15K

Cell (C-1)

$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002401	0.017215	0.007205	1.06749	0.0004086	0.015223	0.001992	0.035607	3.812
0.003188	0.019702	0.009566	1.06324	0.0005304	0.017045	0.002657	0.043145	3.876
0.004022	0.024458	0.012068	1.06264	0.0005757	0.021012	0.003446	0.055548	3.927
0.004807	0.030311	0.014425	1.06355	0.0005828	0.026087	0.004224	0.067605	3.969
0.005590	0.035833	0.016801	1.06395	0.0006785	0.030912	0.004921	0.079271	2.069
0.006446	0.042832	0.019342	1.06492	0.0006670	0.037054	0.005779	0.093070	2.099
0.007220	0.047294	0.021666	1.06447	0.0007275	0.040801	0.006493	0.103606	2.147

TABLE 4

Temp. 293.15K

Cell (C-1)

$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002401	0.017215	0.007205	1.06891	0.0005620	0.015376	0.001839	0.035301	3.991
0.003188	0.019702	0.009566	1.06459	0.0007006	0.017215	0.002487	0.042805	2.031
0.004022	0.024458	0.012068	1.06401	0.0007996	0.021236	0.003222	0.050335	2.105
0.004807	0.030311	0.014425	1.06495	0.0008631	0.026367	0.003924	0.067045	2.176
0.005599	0.035832	0.016801	1.06530	0.0009260	0.031160	0.004673	0.078777	2.223
0.006446	0.042832	0.019342	1.06631	0.0009809	0.037366	0.005466	0.092444	2.296
0.007220	0.047294	0.021667	1.06587	0.0010823	0.041156	0.006138	0.102901	2.351

TABLE 5

Temp. 298.15K

Cell (C-1)

$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002390	0.017318	0.007172	1.07047	0.0006198	0.015547	0.001771	0.035202	2.057
0.002984	0.022740	0.008955	1.07166	0.0005889	0.020345	0.002395	0.045439	2.056
0.003982	0.028676	0.011950	1.06992	0.0007006	0.025395	0.003282	0.059136	2.132
0.004766	0.033684	0.014301	1.06923	0.0006858	0.029604	0.004080	0.070443	2.124
0.005951	0.038155	0.017856	1.06630	0.0008026	0.033007	0.005148	0.084158	2.174
0.005941	0.043158	0.017829	1.06692	0.0007257	0.037942	0.005216	0.089242	2.190
0.007164	0.047248	0.021602	1.06701	0.0008253	0.040909	0.006339	0.103001	2.220

TABLE 6

Temp. 303.15K

Cell (C-1)

$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002984	0.022740	0.008955	1.07845	0.001051	0.020807	0.019330	0.044452	2.415
0.003982	0.028676	0.011950	1.07174	0.001336	0.026030	0.026465	0.057787	2.516
0.004766	0.033684	0.014301	1.07113	0.015320	0.030450	0.032938	0.068681	2.585
0.005951	0.038155	0.017856	1.06830	0.019390	0.034143	0.040116	0.081886	2.674
0.005941	0.043158	0.017829	1.07185	0.018516	0.039068	0.040898	0.086991	2.715
0.007164	0.047248	0.021502	1.06906	0.022932	0.042377	0.048710	0.099985	2.793

GHOSH, GHOSH & PRASAD : THIRD DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF PHOSPHORIC ACID ETC.

TABLE 7

Temp. 308.15K								Cell (C-1)
$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002432	0.014554	0.007323	1.06860	0.001250	0.013372	0.001182	0.031465	$\bar{2}.463$
0.003183	0.019946	0.009595	1.06955	0.001408	0.018171	0.001775	0.042601	$\bar{2}.513$
0.003975	0.024961	0.011967	1.06954	0.001686	0.022672	0.002289	0.053430	$\bar{2}.611$
0.004762	0.031346	0.014337	1.07071	0.001820	0.028405	0.002941	0.065852	$\bar{2}.668$
0.005569	0.035704	0.016768	1.06997	0.002108	0.032243	0.003461	0.076101	$\bar{2}.741$
0.006354	0.043322	0.020492	1.06977	0.002278	0.039246	0.004076	0.091028	$\bar{2}.812$
0.007594	0.049899	0.022863	1.07047	0.002689	0.044995	0.004905	0.105352	$\bar{2}.899$

TABLE 8

Temp. 313.15K								Cell (C-1)
$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002480	0.018336	0.007437	1.07589	0.001408	0.017264	0.001072	0.035396	$\bar{2}.686$
0.003211	0.023391	0.009635	1.07538	0.001779	0.021959	0.001432	0.045491	$\bar{2}.803$
0.003953	0.028781	0.011863	1.07517	0.002015	0.026842	0.001938	0.055982	$\bar{2}.846$
0.004793	0.030540	0.014383	1.07141	0.002575	0.028322	0.002218	0.064363	$\bar{2}.938$
0.005637	0.035923	0.016916	1.07141	0.003039	0.033326	0.002598	0.074946	$\bar{1}.040$
0.006407	0.042278	0.019226	1.07233	0.003335	0.039205	0.003073	0.086870	$\bar{1}.104$
0.007208	0.047155	0.021629	1.07207	0.003767	0.043714	0.003441	0.096964	$\bar{1}.181$

TABLE 9

Temp. 318.15K								Cell (C-1)
$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002480	0.018336	0.007437	1.07745	0.001588	0.017444	0.000892	0.035014	$\bar{2}.824$
0.003211	0.023391	0.009635	1.07686	0.001970	0.022131	0.012605	0.045170	$\bar{2}.904$
0.003953	0.028781	0.011863	1.07670	0.002280	0.027108	0.016730	0.055849	$\bar{2}.971$
0.004793	0.030540	0.014383	1.07275	0.002711	0.028458	0.020318	0.063877	$\bar{2}.993$
0.005637	0.035923	0.016916	1.07274	0.003203	0.033490	0.024338	0.074618	$\bar{1}.097$
0.006407	0.042278	0.019226	1.07368	0.003546	0.039417	0.028608	0.086472	$\bar{1}.168$
0.007208	0.047155	0.021629	1.07348	0.004098	0.044045	0.031094	0.096646	$\bar{1}.264$

TABLE 10

Temp. 323.15K								Cell (C-1)
$m_{\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4}$	m_{NaOH}	m_{NaCl}	E in abs. volt	m_{HPO_4}	m_{OH}	m_{PO_4}	μ	$\log K_{\text{H}} + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$
0.002480	0.018336	0.007437	1.07877	0.001711	0.017568	0.000769	0.034702	$\bar{2}.927$
0.003211	0.023391	0.009635	1.07816	0.002092	0.022273	0.001118	0.044816	$\bar{2}.984$
0.003953	0.028781	0.011863	1.07801	0.002455	0.027282	0.001498	0.055502	$\bar{1}.054$
0.004793	0.030540	0.014383	1.07402	0.002926	0.028672	0.001867	0.063043	$\bar{1}.079$
0.005637	0.035923	0.016916	1.07400	0.003420	0.033706	0.002217	0.074185	$\bar{1}.171$
0.006407	0.042278	0.019226	1.07492	0.003739	0.039610	0.026680	0.086061	$\bar{1}.227$
0.007208	0.047155	0.021629	1.07680	0.004274	0.044221	0.029336	0.096274	$\bar{1}.313$

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_H + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}}$ against μ .

TABLE 11— pK_h OF PO_4^{3-} AND pK_s OF H_3PO_4

Temp/K	pK_h	$\beta'_s/\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ kg}$	pK_w	pK_s
283.15	2.495 ± 0.019	3.33 ± 0.27	14.538	12.043
288.15	2.345 ± 0.021	4.84 ± 0.29	14.350	12.005
293.15	2.195 ± 0.010	5.33 ± 0.11	14.170	11.979
298.15	2.040 ± 0.023	2.53 ± 0.25	14.002	11.962
303.15	1.885 ± 0.009	6.81 ± 0.12	13.842	11.959
308.15	1.725 ± 0.014	6.00 ± 0.18	13.690	11.957
313.15	1.580 ± 0.024	7.95 ± 0.35	13.462	11.957
318.15	1.420 ± 0.021	6.92 ± 0.30	13.398	11.977
323.15	1.285 ± 0.015	6.16 ± 0.21	13.263	11.971

These values of pK_s are also recorded in Table 11. As the e.m.f. values are correct to ± 0.025 mV the pK_s are correct to 0.008 units.

The values of pK_s obtained between 283.15K and 323.15K fit in equation (8) to an accuracy of 0.01.

$$pK_s = \frac{2397.4}{T} + 4.2364 - 2.6061 \times 10^{-2}T + 8.3834 \times 10^{-5}T^2 \quad \dots (8)$$

The values of thermodynamic quantities such as ΔG_s^0 , ΔH_s^0 , ΔS_s^0 and ΔCp_s^0 accompanying the dissociation of 1 mole of HPO_4^{2-} were computed statistically from equation (8). These values are recorded in Table 12.

Our ΔH_s^0 value ($1237 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$) at 298.15K is somewhat lower than ΔH_s^0 values given by Pitzer²⁰ viz., $3500 \pm 500 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$ obtained calorimetrically and $5.8 \pm 0.8 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (from K_3PO_4) and 4.8 ± 0.3

TABLE 12—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF $HPO_4^{2-} \rightleftharpoons H^+ + PO_4^{3-}$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp/K	$\Delta H_s^0/\text{J mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta G_s^0/\text{J mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta S_s^0/\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$	$\Delta Cp_s^0/\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$
283.15	13030	65295	-185	-490
288.15	10528	66240	-193	-512
293.15	7907	67229	-202	-535
298.15	5175	68264	-212	-559
303.15	2320	69347	-221	-583
308.15	-653	70475	-231	-607
313.15	-3749	71654	-241	-632
318.15	-6971	72883	-251	-657
323.15	-10323	74166	-261	-683

kcal mol^{-1} (from Na_3PO_4) obtained from laser studies¹⁰. Our ΔH_s^0 value at 303.15K is also lower than ΔH_s^0 value given by Millero, Duer, Shepard and Chetirkin²¹. It is known that ΔH_s^0 found by e.m.f. and that found by direct calorimetric measurement are sometimes discrepant²² and should be discrepant, because in calorimetric method we cannot be very sure of the extent of reaction.

References

1. E. B. R. PRIDEAUX and A. T. WARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 423.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1927, **46**, 350.
3. J. SENDROY and A. B. HASTINGS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, **71**, 783.
4. M. JOWETT and H. MILLET, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1004.
5. I. N. KUGELMASS, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, **23**, 587.
6. N. BJERRUM and A. UNMACK, *Kgl. Danske Videnskab. Selskab, Math-fys Medd.*, 1929, **9**, 5.
7. R. C. WELLS, *J. Wash. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, **32**, 321.
8. N. KONOPIK and O. LEBERAL, *Monatsh*, 1949, **80**, 655.
9. C. E. VANDERZEE and A. S. QUIST, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 118.
10. C. M. PRESTON and W. A. ADAMS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1979, **83**, 814.
11. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis*, 3rd edition, 575, 242 and 460.
12. G. D. PINCHING and R. G. BATES, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1946, **37**, 311.
13. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 416.
14. G. J. HILLS and D. J. G. IVES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 305.
15. D. J. G. IVES and G. J. JANZ, editor, *Reference Electrode*, Academic Press, 1961, 95.

GHOSH, GHOSH & PRASAD : THIRD DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF PHOSPHORIC ACID ETC.

16. A. K. GHOSH, J. C. GHOSH and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 489.
17. R. G. BATES, *Electrometric pH determination*, Wiley, New York, 1954, 313.
18. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2179.
19. G. G. MANOV, R. G. BATES, W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1765.
20. K. S. PITZER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 2365.
21. F. J. MILLERO, W. C. DURR, E. SHEPARD and P. V. CHETIRKIN, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 1978, **7**, 877.
22. (a) R. N. GOLDBERG and L. G. HEPLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4654.
(b) A. K. GOVINGTON, M. I. A. FERRA and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. C. S. Faraday I*, 1977, **73**, 1721.
(c) S. BANDOPADHAYA and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 76.